

Rating the best cell phones with multi-criteria analysis tools (CRITIC and AHP)

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Abstract

The present research work applies different methods of multi-criteria analysis, to identify which is the best cell phone manufactured by the best companies worldwide, in the year 2021. The methods applied are: a) Quantitative method AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) in Spanish Hierarchical Analytical Process proposed by Thomas Saaty in 1980. b) METHOD CRITIC (CRiteria Importance Through Intercriteria Correlation).

The work in question will be divided into four sections, the first is the Introduction, where it will be quickly addressed what is intended to be done in the research. In the Theoretical Framework section, the research related to the subject is explained. As a third point the Methodology, the way to apply the methodologies and the results obtained in this study is explained. To finalize the Results and Discussion, the results obtained will be analyzed, such as the differences between each model.

INTRODUCTION

The objective of this research work is to apply multi-criteria analysis tools for an objective assessment of the best cell phones related to the year 2021. For the study, the best five models of phones were taken, from the different brands worldwide, among the brands to be analyzed are: Model 1, Model 2, Model 3, Model 4, Model 5. It is worth mentioning that only on this occasion the brands to be analyzed will be mentioned, from this point it will be avoided to mention the models, and the order in which they will appear will be random. While there are a lot of features that can be analyzed, we will focus on the five features that we believe are the most important such as: Design, Screen, Performance, Battery, Cameras. The same ones that positively impact the final score of the device.(Martí, 2022)

It is necessary to remember that the main objective of any standard multi-criteria decision-making analysis (MCDM) is to evaluate and classify the available alternatives based on a predetermined set of decision criteria. There are four fundamental stages in the execution of an MCDM analysis, so that decision makers identify all relevant criteria that can be used to evaluate alternatives, identification can be made by reviewing the literature, based on the knowledge of decision makers, or seeking expert advice. Decision makers must invest a lot of time at this stage because the omission of any prominent criteria will result in useless analysis.(Sitorus et al., 2019)(Parameshwaran et al., 2015)(Krishnan et al., 2021)

Many popular device websites provide a list of crucial criteria for smartphone selection, some even rank these criteria from the most to the least important. Since the smartphone market is becoming increasingly competitive, providing information according to this topic will certainly be useful for manufacturers to develop the right product strategies to stay in such a competitive market.(Versus, n.a..)

There are several MCDM-based studies conducted to scientifically determine the weights and ranges of smartphone criteria. For example, they evaluated various smartphone criteria, including screen dimension and resolution, using the combination of AHP and data surround analysis. Meanwhile, it analyzed responses collected from a sample of customers using a modified AHP to evaluate eight selected criteria, including screen quality, camera, and price. In another study, it applied both the diffuse AHP and the fuzzy analytical network process for a similar purpose of evaluating smartphone criteria.Peaw and Mustafa (2006)Ho et al. (2016)Okfalisa et al. (2020)

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The CRITIC method, in Spanish Importance of CRiterios through the correlation between criteria, proposed in 1985 by the authors Diakoulaki, Mavrotas and Papayannakis (Aznar & Guijarro, 2012; Polytechnic University of Valencia, n.a.) . Original uses the standard deviation to measure the contrast intensity of each criterion (Vujičić et al., 2017). The method ensures that a criterion with a higher contrast intensity or standard deviation is assigned with a greater weight. The logic of this scenario can be explained as follows. If the scores of one criterion show more variation from one alternative to another, this criterion is expected to provide more interesting or meaningful information. In general, it can be said that the CRITIC method assigns greater weight to a criterion that has a higher contrast intensity and a greater degree of conflict with other criteria. Because of this aspect, CRITIC has been used in many real applications. Previous studies also show that CRITIC has been used in conjunction with other objective or subjective methods for weight determination. For example, it used a combination of a peer comparison method and CRITIC to evaluate the weights of the logistics location selection criteria. used the fuzzy PIPRECIA method and the CRITIC method to measure the weights of the bank performance criteria. applied a combination of an entropy method and CRITIC to determine the weight of indoor air quality criteria. (Zolfani et al., 2020) (Yerlikaya et al., 2019) (Marković et al., 2020) (Piasecki & Kostyrko, 2020)

There are four fundamental stages in the execution of an MCDM analysis, in the first stage, decision makers identify all relevant criteria that can be used to evaluate alternatives, identification can be made by reviewing the literature, based on the knowledge of decision makers, or seeking expert advice. Decision makers must invest a lot of time at this stage because the omission of any prominent criteria will result in useless analysis. (Parameshwaran et al., 2015) (Krishnan et al., 2021)

In the second stage, decision makers must collect the data of each alternative with respect to all the criteria identified in the previous stage to form the decision matrix. Suppose an MCDM problem where $a_i = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ denotes the set of alternatives under investigation and $c_j = (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)$ represents the set of evaluation criteria. The general form of the decision matrix can be expressed, where x_{mn} denotes the score of the alternative m with respect to criterion n . (Jankowski, 1995)

In the third stage, the weight of each criterion is determined. It is worth noting that it does not make sense to treat all criteria equally since they can actually have different

degrees of importance in a decision system. In the final stage, the weights of these criteria and the local scores belonging to each alternative are aggregated into an overall score. Based on these overall scores, alternatives can be sorted from the most preferred to the least preferred. The focus of this document is on the third stage, which is the weight determination stage. Inaccurate weights will result in misleading global scores, causing us to choose an inappropriate alternative or solution to the decision problem. One, therefore, must be extremely cautious when determining weights. Unfortunately, this process can quickly morph into a complex one, especially when the decision problem involves many criteria. Therefore, several methods have been proposed to determine the weights of the criteria systematically.(Md Saad et al., 2014)(Krishnan et al., 2015)(Krishnan et al., 2021)

The Hierarchical Analytical Process (AHP) is a structured technique for dealing with complex decisions, was developed by Thomas L. Saaty in the seventies (70s) and has been extensively studied and refined, ever since. (Moreno, n.a.; Sarmiento, 2014) It is a mathematical method created to evaluate alternatives when several criteria are taken into consideration and is based on the principle that the experience and knowledge of the actors are as important as the data used in the process. The first uses of AHP were given in the solution of decision problems in multi-criteria environments. The implementation of the AHP proposes four fundamental steps or stages:(Saaty & Kearns, 1985)

1. Define the problem.
2. Define the hierarchical decision structure.
3. Construct the matrices of peer judgments
4. Apply the priorities obtained to set priorities across the different levels of the structure

A hierarchy in the AHP methodology consists of a first level of objective, a group of alternatives to achieve that objective, and a group of criteria that relate the alternatives to the objective. These criteria can in turn be divided into sub-criteria, as much as the problem requires. (Fontalvo et al., 2018).

METHODOLOGY

After having carried out a review of the theoretical framework we identified two methods CRITIC and AHP that will allow us to identify the best cell phones in the year 2021. We proceeded to find optimal criteria that meet the buyer's need. Then a respective assessment was given with respect to the Saaty scale and then a matrix was made in which the respective valuations are evidenced.

CRITIC Method

Table 1: Valuation of Variables

	Design	Screen	Yield	Cameras	Battery
Model 1	93	61	89	76	52
Model 2	97	14	15	30	46
Model 3	91	82	88	73	52
Model 4	42	53	66	62	47
Model 5	63	28	80	62	48
SUM	386	238	338	303	245
MAXIMUM	97	82	89	76	52
MINIMAL	42	14	15	30	46

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 2: Standardization by Range

	Design	Screen	Yield	Cameras	Battery
Model 1	0,92727	0,691176	1	1	1
Model 2	1	0	0	0	0
Model 3	0,89090	1	0,98648	0,93478	1
Model 4	0	0,573529	0,68918	0,69565	0,16666
Model 5	0,38181	0,205882	0,87837	0,69565	0,33333

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 3: Standard Deviation

0,38764387	0,354481931	0,37240458	0,3547144	0,42163702
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Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 4: Correlation Coefficient

	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5
Column 1	1				
Column 2	0,042574	1			
Column 3	-0,184359	0,75396	1		
Column 4	-0,149820	0,83454	0,98172	1	
Column 5	0,42271	0,82976	0,78603	0,82851	1

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 5: Correlation Deviation

Design	1,499751
Screen	0,545599
Yield	0,619174
Cameras	0,533858
Battery	0,477698

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 6: Normalized weighting

	Weightings	Weighting Standard
Design	1,49975	0,4079
Screen	0,54559	0,1484
Yield	0,61917	0,1684
Cameras	0,53385	0,1452
Battery	0,47769	0,1299
SUM	3,67608	

Prepared by: The Researchers

RESULTS

Table 7: CRITICAL Results

	Design	Screen	Yield	Cameras	Battery	Company weighting	Standard Weighting
Model 1	0,92727	0,691176	1	1	1	0,92449	0,3002
Model 2	1	0	0	0	0	0,40797	0,1325
Model 3	0,89090	1	0,98648	0,93478	1	0,94374	0,3065
Model 4	0	0,573529	0,68918	0,69565	0,16666	0,32388	0,1052
Model 5	0,38181	0,205882	0,87837	0,69565	0,33333	0,47861	0,1554
	0,40797	0,148418	0,16843	0,14522	0,12994	3,07872	

Prepared by: The Researchers

AHP METHOD

Table 8: Paired matrix of criteria

	Design	Screen	Yield	Cameras	Battery
Design	1	3	1/5	1/7	1/9
Screen	1/3	1	1/5	1/3	1/7
Yield	5	5	1	7	3
Cameras	7	3	1/7	1	1/7
Battery	9	7	1/3	7	1
SUM	22,33	19,00	1,88	15,48	4,40

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 9: Standardization

	Design	Screen	Yield	Cameras	Battery	EIGENVECTOR - WEIGHTING
Design	0,04	0,16	0,11	0,01	0,03	0,07
Screen	0,01	0,05	0,11	0,02	0,03	0,05
Yield	0,22	0,26	0,53	0,45	0,68	0,43
Cameras	0,31	0,16	0,08	0,06	0,03	0,13
Battery	0,40	0,37	0,18	0,45	0,23	0,33

Prepared by: The Researchers

DESIGN

Table 10: Design Valuation

Design	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Model 1	1	1/5	5	7	5
Model 2	5	1	7	5	9
Model 3	1/5	1/7	1	7	5
Model 4	1/7	1/5	1/7	1	1/7
Model 5	1/5	1/9	1/5	7	1
SUM	6,54	1,65	13,34	27,00	20,14

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 11: Design Weighting

Design	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Weighting
Model 1	0,15	0,12	0,37	0,26	0,25	0,23
Model 2	0,76	0,60	0,52	0,19	0,45	0,51
Model 3	0,03	0,09	0,07	0,26	0,25	0,14
Model 4	0,02	0,12	0,01	0,04	0,01	0,04
Model 5	0,03	0,07	0,01	0,26	0,05	0,08

Prepared by: The Researchers

SCREEN

Table 12: Screen Valorization

Screen	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Model 1	1	5	1/7	3	9
Model 2	1/5	1	1/5	1/7	1/3
Model 3	7	5	1	9	7
Model 4	1/3	7	1/9	1	5
Model 5	1/9	3	1/7	1/5	1
SUM	8,64	21,00	1,60	13,34	22,33

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 13: Screen Weighting

Screen	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Weighting
Model 1	0,12	0,24	0,09	0,22	0,40	0,21
Model 2	0,02	0,05	0,13	0,01	0,01	0,04
Model 3	0,81	0,24	0,63	0,67	0,31	0,53
Model 4	0,04	0,33	0,07	0,07	0,22	0,15
Model 5	0,01	0,14	0,09	0,01	0,04	0,06

Prepared by: The Researchers

YIELD

Table 14: Performance Valuation

Yield	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Model 1	1	9	3	5	3
Model 2	1/9	1	1/7	1/7	1/9
Model 3	1/3	7	1	5	3
Model 4	1/5	7	1/5	1	1/3
Model 5	1/3	9	1/3	3	1
SUM	1,98	33,00	4,68	14,14	7,44

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 15: Performance Weighting

Yield	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Weighting
Model 1	0,51	0,27	0,64	0,35	0,40	0,44
Model 2	0,06	0,03	0,03	0,01	0,01	0,03
Model 3	0,17	0,21	0,21	0,35	0,40	0,27
Model 4	0,10	0,21	0,04	0,07	0,04	0,09
Model 5	0,17	0,27	0,07	0,21	0,13	0,17

Prepared by: The Researchers

CAMERAS

Table 16: Camera Valuation

Cameras	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Model 1	1	7	3	5	5
Model 2	1/7	1	1/7	1/5	1/5
Model 3	1/3	7	1	5	7
Model 4	1/5	5	1/5	1	3
Model 5	1/5	5	1/7	1/3	1
SUM	1,88	25,00	4,49	11,53	16,20

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 17: Weighting of Chambers

Cameras	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Weighting
Model 1	0,53	0,28	0,67	0,43	0,31	0,44
Model 2	0,08	0,04	0,03	0,02	0,01	0,04
Model 3	0,18	0,28	0,22	0,43	0,43	0,31
Model 4	0,11	0,20	0,04	0,09	0,19	0,12
Model 5	0,11	0,20	0,03	0,03	0,06	0,09

Prepared by: The Researchers

BATTERY

Table 18: Battery Recovery

Battery	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Model 1	1	5	3	5	3
Model 2	1/5	1	1/5	1/3	1/3
Model 3	1/3	5	1	7	9
Model 4	1/5	3	1/7	1	1/5
Model 5	1/3	3	1/9	5	1
SUM	2,07	17,00	4,45	18,33	13,53

Prepared by: The Researchers

Table 19: Battery Weighting

Battery	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Weighting
Model 1	0,48	0,29	0,67	0,27	0,22	0,39
Model 2	0,10	0,06	0,04	0,02	0,02	0,05
Model 3	0,16	0,29	0,22	0,38	0,67	0,35
Model 4	0,10	0,18	0,03	0,05	0,01	0,07
Model 5	0,16	0,18	0,02	0,27	0,07	0,14

Prepared by: The Researchers

RESULTS

Table 20: AHP Results

	Design	Screen	Yield	Cameras	Battery	Prioritization
Model 1	0,23	0,21	0,44	0,44	0,39	0,397
Model 2	0,51	0,04	0,03	0,04	0,05	0,069
Model 3	0,14	0,53	0,27	0,31	0,35	0,303
Model 4	0,04	0,15	0,09	0,12	0,07	0,091
Model 5	0,08	0,06	0,17	0,09	0,14	0,140
Weighting	0,07	0,05	0,43	0,13	0,33	

Prepared by: The Researchers

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

CRITIC Method

Of the results obtained from the weighting, the results were ordered in a ranking from 1 to 5, with 1 being the largest and 5 the worst. The results that are obtained in table 21, tells us that the brand with the best mobile device to buy in 2021, with respect to the characteristics previously analyzed are: Model 3 because it presents its customers with a new experience in addition to having special features in their designs, followed by Model 1 it offers an exclusivity to its customers, has its own operating system, and finally Model 5 that offers excellent features and adjusted price, with good features that face the cell phones of world knowledge and popular in the market.

Table 21: Ranking of CRITIC results

	Standard Weighting	Ranking
Model 1	0,3002	2
Model 2	0,1325	4
Model 3	0,3065	1
Model 4	0,1052	5
Model 5	0,1554	3

Prepared by: The Researchers

AHP Method

Of the results obtained from the weighting, we proceeded to order the results in a ranking from 1 to 5, with 1 being the largest and 5 the worst. The results that are observed in table 22, tells us that the brand with the best mobile device to buy in 2021, with respect to the characteristics previously analyzed are: Model 1 since it provides exclusivity to its customers, in addition to having its own operating system, something characteristic of this brand is that they present their innovative designs once a year. On the contrary, Model 3 presents its customers with a new experience with another operating system, and to finish Model 5 undoubtedly use strategies comor other manufacturers, has been to offer excellent features at an adjusted price and good features that face the cell phones of world knowledge and popular in the cell phone market.(Martí, 2022; OE, 2022; Rodriguez, 2022)

Table 22: Ranking of AHP results

	Prioritization	Ranking
Model 1	0,397	1
Model 2	0,069	5
Model 3	0,303	2
Model 4	0,091	4
Model 5	0,140	3
Weighting		

Prepared by: The Researchers

Discussion

There is a clear difference between the results of both methods, however, the difference observed in the first three becauseough is not much, so these methods are free to application and interpretation regardless of their applicators.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Aznar, J., & Guijarro, F. (2012). *NEW VALUATION METHODS MULTICRITERIA MODELS*. <https://institutodevaluacion.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/NUEVOS-ME%CC%81TODOS-DE-VALORACIO%CC%81N-MODELOS-MULTICRITERIO.pdf>
- Fontalvo, R., Traeger, W., & Guevara, Y. (2018, March). *Application of AHP and PL methodology for the purchase of a cell phone. working paper*. Research Gate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323825817_Application_of_AHP_and_PL_methodology_for_the_purchase_of_a_cell_phone_working_paper
- Ho, F., Wang, C. N., Ho, C. T., Chiang, Y. C., & Huang, Y. F. (2016). Evaluation of Smartphone feature preference by a modified AHP approach. *IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management, 2016-January*, 591–594. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEM.2015.7385716>
- Jankowski, P. (1995). Integrating geographical information systems and multiple criteria decision-making methods. *International Journal of Geographical Information Systems*, 9(3), 251–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02693799508902036>
- Krishnan, A. R., Kasim, M. M., & Bakar, E. M. N. E. A. (2015). A Short Survey on the Usage of Choquet Integral and its Associated Fuzzy Measure in Multiple Attribute Analysis. *Procedia Computer Science*, 59, 427–434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROCS.2015.07.560>
- Krishnan, A. R., Kasim, M. M., Hamid, R., & Ghazali, M. F. (2021). A Modified CRITIC Method to Estimate the Objective Weights of Decision Criteria. *Symmetry*, 13(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym13060973>
- Marković, V., Stajić, L., Stević, Ž., Mitrović, G., Novarlić, B., & Radojičić, Z. (2020). A Novel Integrated Subjective-Objective MCDM Model for Alternative Ranking in Order to Achieve Business Excellence and Sustainability. *Symmetry 2020, Vol. 12, Page 164, 12(1)*, 164. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SYM12010164>

- Martí, A. (2022, January 17). *The best mobiles of the year (2021): their analysis and videos are here*. Engadget. <https://www.xataka.com/analisis/mejores-moviles-ano-2021-analisis-videos>
- Md Saad, R., Ahmad, M. Z., Abu, M. S., & Jusoh, M. S. (2014). Hamming distance method with subjective and objective weights for personnel selection. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/865495>
- Moreno, M. (n.d.). *THE HIERARCHICAL ANALYTICAL PROCESS (AHP). FUNDAMENTALS, METHODOLOGY AND APPLICATIONS*. Retrieved July 13, 2022, from [https://users.dcc.uchile.cl/~nbaloian/DSS-DCC/ExplanationMethodAHP\(ve%20rpaginas11-16\).pdf](https://users.dcc.uchile.cl/~nbaloian/DSS-DCC/ExplanationMethodAHP(ve%20rpaginas11-16).pdf)
- OE. (2022). *What are the best brands of cell phones in this 2022?* OEchsl. <https://www.oechsle.pe/inspira/marcas-de-celulares-2021/>
- Okfalisa, O., Rusnedy, H., Iswavigra, D. U., Pranggono, B., Haerani, E. H., & Saktioto, S. (2020). DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM FOR SMARTPHONE RECOMMENDATION: THE COMPARISON OF FUZZY AHP AND FUZZY ANP IN MULTI-ATTRIBUTE DECISION MAKING. *SINERGI*, 25(1), 101–110. <https://doi.org/10.22441/SINERGI.2021.1.013>
- Parameshwaran, R., Praveen Kumar, S., & Saravanakumar, K. (2015). An integrated fuzzy MCDM based approach for robot selection considering objective and subjective criteria. *Applied Soft Computing*, 26, 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ASOC.2014.09.025>
- Peaw, T. L., & Mustafa, A. (2006). *Incorporating AHP in DEA Analysis for Smartphone Comparisons*.
- Piasecki, M., & Kostyrko, K. (2020). Development of Weighting Scheme for Indoor Air Quality Model Using a Multi-Attribute Decision Making Method. *Energies* 2020, Vol. 13, Page 3120, 13(12), 3120. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN13123120>
- Rodriguez, E. (2022, July 15). *In search of the best mobiles MODEL 5: buying guide depending on budget, tastes and quality price*. Engadget. <https://www.xataka.com/seleccion/busca-mejores-moviles-Modelo-5-guide-buy-function-budget-tastes-quality-price>

- Saaty, T., & Kearns, K. (1985). The Analytic Hierarchy Process. *Analytical Planning*, 19–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-032599-6.50008-8>
- Sarmiento, L. E. (2014). Analysis and study of cellular mobile devices through selection, evaluation and prospecting methodologies to support new cellular mobile digital content, cellular mobile applications and cellular mobile services for the Colombian case [National University of Colombia]. In *Universidad Nacional de Colombia*. <https://repositorio.unal.edu.co/handle/unal/55551>
- Sitorus, F., Cilliers, J. J., & Brito-Parada, P. R. (2019). Multi-criteria decision making for the choice problem in mining and mineral processing: Applications and trends. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 121, 393–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ESWA.2018.12.001>
- Polytechnic University of Valencia. (n.a.). *CRITIC method*. Retrieved July 13, 2022, from <https://media.upv.es/player/?id=172ee406-df70-934d-960a-f63ad7c6a163>
- Versus. (n.a.). *Huawei B199 vs iPhone 13 vs Model 2 Galaxy S21 vs Model 2 Z4 vs Xiaomi Redmi Note 10S | Comparison of mobile phones*. VERSUS. Retrieved July 12, 2022, from <https://versus.com/es/huawei-b199-vs-iphone-13-vs-Model-2-galaxy-s21-vs-Model-2-z4-vs-xiaomi-redmi-note-10s>
- Vujičić, M. D., Papić, M. Z., & Blagojević, M. D. (2017). Comparative analysis of objective techniques for criteria weighing in two MCDM methods on example of an air conditioner selection. *Tehnika*, 72(3), 422–429. <https://doi.org/10.5937/TEHNIKA1703422V>
- Yerlikaya, M. A., Tabak, Ç., & Yıldız, K. (2019, July 15). *Logistic Location Selection with Critic-Ahp and Vikor Integrated Approach*. Data Science and Applications. <http://jdatasci.com/index.php/jdatasci/article/view/22>
- Zolfani, S. H., Yazdani, M., Torkayesh, A. E., & Derakhti, A. (2020). Application of a Gray-Based Decision Support Framework for Location Selection of a Temporary Hospital during COVID-19 Pandemic. *Symmetry* 2020, Vol. 12, Page 886, 12(6), 886. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SYM12060886>